

1 **DHCR24, SCD, and other steroid metabolic and biosynthetic enzymes are mobilized during TE**
2 **commitment.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 DHCR24, SCD, and a series of other steroid metabolic enzymes together with likely functions in lineage
10 commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Zhou, E., Ge, X., Nakashima, H., Li, R., van der Zande, H.J., Liu, C., Li, Z., Müller, C., Bracher, F.,
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